

INFRAEDI-02-2018

www.bioexcel.eu

BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D1.2 – Exascale Co-Design Benchmark Cases

WP1: Code optimization & scaling

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Document Information

Deliverable Number	D1.2
Deliverable Name	Exascale co-design benchmark cases
Due Date	2019-07-31 (PM7)
Deliverable Lead	KTH
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Keywords	Benchmarks, co-design
WP	WP1
Nature	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Final Version Date	2019-07-31
Reviewed by	Adam Hospital (IRB) Stian Soiland-Reyes (UNIMAN)
MGT Board Approval	2019-07-31
MGT Board Approval of revision	2020-12-10

Document History

Partner	Date	Comments	Version
KTH	2019-06-07	TOC	0.1
KTH	2019-06-19	Added introduction	0.2
KTH	2019-06-27	Added most GROMACS contents	0.3
UU	2019-06-27	HADDOCK section added	0.4
KTH	2019-06-28	Executive summary + Conclusions and minor updates to HADDOCK & GROMACS	0.5
UEDIN	2019-06-30	Minor corrections, added CP2K contents	0.6
KTH	2019-07-10	GROMACS text updates; minor update to HADDOCK text to refer to Zenodo links in the distribution materials	0.7
UEDIN	2019-07-10	Small changes to CP2K content	0.8
UNIMAN	2019-07-15	Review comments and suggested edits	0.8.1
UU	2019-07-16	Changes in response to review	0.8.2
KTH	2019-07-22	Address GROMACS comments	0.8.3
UEDIN	2019-07-26	Addressed CP2K comments	0.8.4
UEDIN	2019-07-29	Minor changes	0.8.5
KTH	2019-07-30	Added DOIs, resolved final changes	0.9
KTH	2019-07-31	Final formatting for delivery	1.0
KTH	2020-12-10	Minor updates based on reviewers' comments	1.1

Executive Summary

This document describes benchmark cases for co-design for the three main BioExcel application: GROMACS, HADDOCK and CP2K. We have analyzed the performance characteristics of the applications in bio-molecular type use cases and identified the one kernel or component for each code that has the most impact on performance. For GROMACS this is the non-bonded pair kernel, for HADDOCK I/O of many small files and for CP2K computation of the long-range part of the QM/MM potential. Benchmark tools have been built for these kernels/components. This document describes how these benchmarks are set up, how the tools work and discusses example output. The benchmark tools have been constructed such that a limited part of the code base is required. This is important for two reasons. One is that in co-design someone who is neither an expert of the code or the scientific domain should be able focus on the characteristics of the kernel. They should not have to understand, and certainly not benchmark, the whole code base or scientific problem. The second reason is that this makes it much easier to run code in an emulator to either inform hardware design decisions or optimize performance on hardware not yet available. Finally, possible extensions or additions of tools are discussed.

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1 Introduction

Over the last two decades HPC machines have evolved from nodes with a single core scalar processor and a relatively simple file system to much more heterogeneous and hierarchical setups. Nodes can now have extremely high core counts with complex cache hierarchies. Accelerators such as *GPGPUs* (general-purpose graphical processing units) are becoming more common and are likely needed at the Exascale. Both CPUs and accelerators have powerful compute units that can perform many floating-point operations per cycle, but are more difficult to program efficiently. Nowadays I/O is handled by advanced parallel file systems with caches. If data sizes are not too large, in-memory file systems can also be used.

This complexity means that there are even more challenges to optimizing scientific codes for current and future HPC machines. Code owners are often not experts on aspects particular to HPC and optimization only gets harder as architectures become more complex. **Co-design** is the way forward, where domain experts collaborate with HPC experts and/or vendors to improve performance for particular and especially new architectures. But as scientific codes often consist of millions of lines of code, smaller, important components need to be extracted for such co-design efforts.

In an ideal case most time in a code's execution would be spent in a few compute intensive routines, which we will refer to as *simulation kernels*. These routines can then be extracted to study in isolation. However, in practice, and in particular on modern hierarchical architectures, the performance is very much affected by how fast data can be moved into and out of simulation kernels. When the data has been used in a previous computation, knowing the location of its storage critically affects performance. Therefore, design targets must be chosen carefully. In some cases, it might even be impossible to study a kernel in isolation, as it is memory bound and therefore performance depends mainly on the surrounding state of the memory and caches. Other application cases might be dominated by I/O, which is not uncommon in biomolecular sciences where many different molecules or different conformations of molecules might need to be compared.

It is worth considering two different level of co-design. One is where a simulation kernel is ported to or highly optimized for a new architecture by a hardware vendor or experts at a compute center. Here one would ideally have kernel code that is isolated as much as possible to limit the start-up time of the HPC expert, but also to enable it to run in an emulator, so optimization can be done before the actual hardware for a new architecture is ready. A less deep but often no less important approach is optimization of compiler, software stack or even hardware parameters for an application and use case. Because of the complexity of the hardware, many settings, such as for example compiler flags or file system parameters are by default set for the "average" application. Significant performance gains are possible by optimizing such parameters or for instance switching kernel implementations within the application. For this latter case the benchmark case can include more of the real application's code, but it should be clear which clearly delimited aspects of the code are being tested.

Documentation for benchmark cases is critical, as they should be able to be run by people who know very little about the application or its scientific domain. Thus, the documentation should explain clearly what the intent of the case is, how it should be run, what the output of the benchmark tool means, what options there are and precisely what they do.

The distribution materials for this deliverable include documentation, input data and freely licensed code and is available in several forms. It may be found as a tarball on the BioExcel website (at <https://bioexcel.eu/software/code-repositories/>) and permanently archived on Zenodo (at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3354707>). Updates based on co-design feedback will be made available at the BioExcel code repository on GitHub (at <https://github.com/bioexcel/bioexcel-exascale-co-design-benchmarks>). Future versioned releases will be made when warranted.

In the following sections we will discuss the applications and the above-mentioned aspects for the benchmark cases for the different codes.

2 GROMACS Benchmark Apps

2.1 Overview of compute intensive kernels in GROMACS

Molecular dynamics is an extremely compute intensive application which covers a significant fraction of HPC resources used world-wide. Because of the high computational demands, a lot of effort has gone into optimizing the algorithms and code for MD applications. The cost of these efforts has led to a decrease of the number of biomolecular MD codes from one in every research group in the 1990s to a handful of current codes actively being developed world-wide. GROMACS is one of these codes, precisely because it has focused so much on performance, as well as because it has been fully open-source and free from the start. However, continued effort is needed to make GROMACS perform efficiently on future hardware, especially as architectures are developing rapidly with ever wider Single-Instruction Multiple-Data units in CPUs as well as new accelerators.

There have been several developments to lower the barrier for porting, optimization and co-design efforts. Below we describe a tool for benchmarking the most important kernel in GROMACS: the non-bonded pair kernel. We have also recently added a “performance portability” section to the GROMACS developer manual. The relevant part has been reproduced here as the next sub-section.

2.2 Performance portability

The base code of GROMACS is C++14 with some minor components in C. A compliant C++14 compiler is sufficient to compile GROMACS on any platform. For good performance a few more things are needed.

2.2.1 SIMD vectorization

Modern CPUs achieve high floating-point performance through Single-Instruction Multiple-Data (SIMD) vectorization, where a single instruction is applied to (currently) 2 to 16 floating point numbers or integers at once. In general code can be more or less successfully auto-vectorized by the compiler, but for optimal performance it is often necessary to write explicit SIMD intrinsics or to add pragmas to aid the auto-vectorization.

GROMACS uses a different approach, in which all performance-sensitive code can be vectorized with SIMD instructions using a thin SIMD abstraction layer. The documentation of this SIMD layer for the current GROMACS release can be found at <http://manual.gromacs.org/documentation/2019.3/install-guide/index.html#gmx-simd-support>. The implementations for several currently important architectures can be found at <https://github.com/gromacs/gromacs/tree/release-2019/src/gromacs/simd>

The GROMACS SIMD layer serves two purposes. One is to hide SIMD intrinsics behind a C++ interface that supports overloading. This also has the advantage that for many kernels there is only a single version which is templated on value type, so either scalar or SIMD vectorized code can be created at compile time. A second purpose is to isolate some more complex performance-critical operations required in molecular simulations. These are transpose-load and transpose store operations to load and store particle coordinates and forces while changing the ordering between layouts that work well in different parts of the code. There are only a handful of such operations that need to be implemented, but they are quite critical for performance. A major advantage of this setup is that most of the performance porting is confined within this layer and thus little knowledge of the rest of the GROMACS code-base is required.

The SIMD layer has complete unit-test coverage, so correctness is ensured and developers can focus their efforts on optimizing performance. The most important performance target is the non-bonded pair interaction kernel, as usually 60 to 90 percent of the runtime is spent there. This kernel consists mainly of SIMD instructions. Since it is so important for performance, it is highly optimized as well as specialized for different types of computations. To enable easy benchmarks as well as an overview and comparisons of different flavor of the non-bonded kernels, there is a non-bonded kernel benchmarking tool which can be optionally built. Accurate timing is integrated into the tool. More details can be found in the help text of the tool. The non-bonded kernel algorithms currently support 2, 4, 8 and 16 wide SIMD instructions. It is not hard to add support for 32 wide SIMD instructions (at the cost of somewhat lower algorithmic efficiency). If you are interested in 32 wide SIMD non-bonded algorithm support for a new architecture, please contact the GROMACS developers.

In addition to code optimization, there are a few algorithmic choices to optimize. One aspect that affects all SIMD code is the SIMD width. Modern architectures, in particular x86, support multiple SIMD widths. One would hope higher wider SIMD always results in higher throughput, but some processors have lower instruction

throughput with wider SIMD. Complicating matters more, modern processors are thermally limited. Wider SIMD instructions generate more heat, which leads to lower clock speeds. On the GROMACS algorithmic side, a wider SIMD needs more reordering operations and leads to more wasted flops in many kernels. Thus the choice of SIMD width needs to be evaluated for each processor architecture. It can even depend on the particular processor, as different processors have different frequency characteristics. The optimal choice also depends on the simulated system, as that determines the relative weight of different kernels in a simulation. These effects are even stronger when some kernels are off-loaded to an accelerator, since this leaves mostly less SIMD-friendly algorithms on the CPU. For the non-bonded kernels with 8-wide SIMD there is the choice of using a kernel with the full SIMD cluster with called 4xM or the half cluster width called 2xMM. And finally, there is the choice of using analytical or tabulated particle-mesh Ewald electrostatics correction (on modern, wide SIMD architectures analytical is usually always faster). All choices, except for SIMD width, can be made at run time and they can even be tuned for properties of the particular simulation. We are considering building binaries with support for multiple SIMD architectures. Performance of all these options can be compared easily with the aforementioned benchmarking tool.

2.3 Non-bonded kernel benchmark app

We have developed a benchmarking tool that runs the GROMACS CPU non-bonded kernels in isolation on representative inputs of different sizes. All relevant kernel versions are part of this tool and can be benchmarked individually, as well as a set of relevant combinations in one go, as described in more detail below. This tool is part of the GROMACS distribution and will be released with the 2020 release. It is also available in the code distribution and repository associated with this deliverable, namely at https://github.com/bioexcel/bioexcel-exascale-co-design-benchmarks/tree/master/GROMACS/nonbonded_benchmark

The description of the function, capabilities and the options of the tool are provided through the help function on the tool, which are reproduced here.

SYNOPSIS

```
gmx nonbonded_bench [-size <int>] [-nt <int>] [-simd <enum>]
                    [-coulomb <enum>] [-[no]table] [-combrule <enum>] [-[no]halfllj]
                    [-[no]energy] [-[no]all] [-cutoff <real>] [-iter <int>]
                    [-warmup <int>] [-[no]cycles]
```

DESCRIPTION

gmx nonbonded_bench runs benchmarks for one or more so-called Nbnxm non-bonded pair kernels. The non-bonded pair kernels are the most compute intensive part of MD simulations and usually comprise 60 to 90 percent of the runtime. For this reason they are highly optimized and several different setups are available to compute the same physical interactions. In addition, there are different physical treatments of Coulomb interactions and optimizations for atoms without Lennard-Jones interactions. There are also different physical treatments of Lennard-Jones interactions, but only a plain cut-off is supported in this tool, as that is by far the most common treatment. And finally, while force output is always necessary, energy output is only required at certain steps. In total there are 12 relevant combinations of options. The combinations double to 24 when two different SIMD setups are

supported. These combinations can be run with a single invocation using the `-all` option. The behavior of each kernel is affected by caching behavior, which is determined by the hardware used together with the system size and the cut-off radius. The larger the number of atoms per thread, the more L1 cache is needed to avoid L1 cache misses. The cut-off radius mainly affects the data reuse: a larger cut-off results in more data reuse and makes the kernel less sensitive to cache misses.

OpenMP parallelization is used to utilize multiple hardware threads within a compute node. In these benchmarks there is no interaction between threads, apart from starting and closing a single OpenMP parallel region per iteration. Additionally, threads interact through sharing and evicting data from shared caches. The number of threads to use is set with the `-nt` option. Thread affinity is important, especially with SMT and shared caches. Affinities can be set through the OpenMP library using the `GOMP_CPU_AFFINITY` environment variable.

The benchmark tool times one or more kernels by running them repeatedly for a number of iterations set by the `-iter` option. An initial kernel call is done to avoid additional initial cache misses. Times are recording in cycles read from efficient, high accuracy counters in the CPU. Note that these often do not correspond to actual clock cycles. For each kernel, the tool reports the total number of cycles, the cycles per iteration, and the (total and useful) number of pair interactions per cycle. Because a cluster pair list is used instead of an atom pair list, interactions are also computed for some atom pairs that are beyond the cut-off distance. These pairs are not useful (except for additional buffering, but that is not of interest here), only a side effect of the cluster-pair setup. The SIMD 2xMM kernel has a higher useful pair ratio than the 4xM kernel due to a smaller cluster size, but a lower total pair throughput. It is best to run this, or for that matter any, benchmark with locked CPU clocks, as thermal throttling can significantly affect performance. If that is not an option, the `-warmup` option can be used to run initial, untimed iterations to warm up the processor.

The most relevant regime is between 0.1 to 1 millisecond per iteration. Thus it is useful to run with system sizes that cover both ends of this regime.

The `-simd` and `-table` options select different implementations to compute the same physics. The choice of these options should ideally be optimized for the target hardware. Historically, we only found tabulated Ewald correction to be useful on 2-wide SIMD or 4-wide SIMD without FMA support. As all modern architectures are wider and support FMA, we do not use tables by default. The only exceptions are kernels without SIMD, which only support tables. Options `-coulomb`, `-combrule` and `-half lj` depend on the force field and composition of the simulated system. The optimization of computing Lennard-Jones interactions for only half of the atoms in a cluster is useful for water, which does not use Lennard-Jones on hydrogen atoms in most water models. In the MD engine, any clusters where at most half of the atoms have LJ interactions will automatically use this kernel. And finally, the `-energy` option selects the computation of energies, which are usually only needed infrequently.

OPTIONS

Other options:

```
-size <int> (1)
    The system size is 3000 atoms times this value
-nt <int> (1)
    The number of OpenMP threads to use
-simd <enum> (auto)
    SIMD type, auto runs all supported SIMD setups or no SIMD when SIMD
    is not supported: auto, no, 4xm, 2xmm
-coulomb <enum> (ewald)
    The functional form for the Coulomb interactions: ewald,
    reaction-field
-[no]table (no)
```

```

        Use lookup table for Ewald correction instead of analytical
-combrule <enum>                (geometric)
        The LJ combination rule: geometric, lb, none
-[no]halflj                    (no)
        Use optimization for LJ on half of the atoms
-[no]energy                    (no)
        Compute energies in addition to forces
-[no]all                        (no)
        Run all 12 combinations of options for coulomb, halflj, combrule
-cutoff <real>                 (1)
        Pair-list and interaction cut-off distance
-iter <int>                    (100)
        The number of iterations for each kernel
-warmup <int>                 (0)
        The number of iterations for initial warmup
-[no]cycles                    (no)
        Report cycles/pair instead of pairs/cycle

```

To illustrate what information the tool provides, we show example output for a popular Intel Skylake processor using 8 threads on 4 cores with Hyperthreading and AVX2 256-bit instructions, which allows for the use of both the so-called 4xM and 2xMM non-bonded kernels in GROMACS:

```

SIMD width:          8
System size:        3000 atoms
Cut-off radius:     1 nm
Number of threads:  8
Number of iterations: 1000
Compute energies:   no
Ewald excl. corr.: analytical

```

	Coulomb	LJ	comb.	SIMD	Mcycles	Mcycles/it.	pairs/cycle	
							total	useful
Ewald	all	geom.	4xM	888.187	0.8882	1.5420	0.7090	
Ewald	all	geom.	2xMM	892.942	0.8929	1.3331	0.7052	
Ewald	all	LB	4xM	877.662	0.8777	1.5605	0.7175	
Ewald	all	LB	2xMM	882.020	0.8820	1.3496	0.7140	
Ewald	all	none	4xM	1178.778	1.1788	1.1619	0.5342	
Ewald	all	none	2xMM	1045.149	1.0451	1.1389	0.6025	
Ewald	half	geom.	4xM	826.376	0.8264	1.6574	0.7621	
Ewald	half	geom.	2xMM	853.963	0.8540	1.3939	0.7374	
Ewald	half	LB	4xM	828.442	0.8284	1.6532	0.7602	
Ewald	half	LB	2xMM	861.457	0.8615	1.3818	0.7310	
Ewald	half	none	4xM	1003.646	1.0036	1.3646	0.6275	
Ewald	half	none	2xMM	919.996	0.9200	1.2938	0.6845	
RF	all	geom.	4xM	592.848	0.5928	2.3102	1.0622	
RF	all	geom.	2xMM	708.376	0.7084	1.6804	0.8890	
RF	all	LB	4xM	592.614	0.5926	2.3111	1.0627	
RF	all	LB	2xMM	722.542	0.7225	1.6474	0.8716	
RF	all	none	4xM	905.826	0.9058	1.5120	0.6952	
RF	all	none	2xMM	910.280	0.9103	1.3077	0.6918	
RF	half	geom.	4xM	539.956	0.5400	2.5365	1.1663	
RF	half	geom.	2xMM	650.771	0.6508	1.8291	0.9677	
RF	half	LB	4xM	548.764	0.5488	2.4958	1.1476	
RF	half	LB	2xMM	638.132	0.6381	1.8653	0.9869	
RF	half	none	4xM	695.561	0.6956	1.9691	0.9054	
RF	half	none	2xMM	747.215	0.7472	1.5930	0.8428	

From this output one can see that there are many different kernels and that they show relatively large differences in performance when computing interactions between the same atom pairs. This tool allows for easy comparison of all the

kernels and makes it easier to identify potential performance issues. The tool has already proven useful for GROMACS developers. With the currently very popular AVX2_256 SIMD instruction set on Intel processors, GROMACS uses 4xM non-bonded kernels by default. This was optimal for all cases on Intel Haswell and Broadwell architectures. But on Skylake 2xMM is 10% faster when Ewald is used for Coulomb and there are no Lennard-Jones combination rules. As stated in the help text, the 2xMM kernel has lower raw atom-pair throughput (the “total” column in the output), but can have higher effective throughput (the “useful” column in the output) because of higher algorithmic efficiency. One would like to optimize these settings, but there are currently too many different architectures to do this manually. Auto-tuning during simulation would be the best option, but more refactoring is needed in GROMACS to be able to implement this.

One aspect which we did not discuss up until now is the performance of the non-bonded kernels on accelerators. This is an important performance target. However, writing a benchmark tool for this is difficult due to several reasons. The main reason is that code for accelerators such as GPUs often needs to be tailored for the specific hardware and/or framework. Another reason is that in actual use cases there are often many different kernels running simultaneously on a GPU, which somewhat limits the usefulness of benchmarking a GPU running a single kernel. Nonetheless, a GPU version of the kernel benchmark tool would be useful, also for the GROMACS code owners. We therefore plan to extend the tool with GPU support, but some more refactoring of the GPU initialization in GROMACS is required to achieve this.

2.4 Non-bonded kernel co-design app

It is clear that the non-bonded kernel benchmark tool is very useful for performance porting and tuning. But when developing new architectures, CPU designs are first tested in simulators. It might be too much effort to build or run the complete, or a significant part of, the GROMACS code base in an emulator. Therefore, we have extracted the kernels themselves as well as their inputs into a stand-alone app. The app is built from the minimal GROMACS code needed to run the benchmarks. This enables quicker and simpler co-design of GROMACS for future architectures.

The co-design app has similar functionality as the benchmark tool described in the previous section, except that only a single system size is supported and only the most important kind of kernel is currently supported. The fixed, same system size is not a limitation when running on an emulator, because on an emulator one does not need to run with large numbers of threads as would be needed on a large multicore processor to assess thermally limited performance.

As for the benchmark tool, in future we will consider adding SIMD-accelerated and/or accelerator-based version of the kernel benchmark app. Although the same limitations for accelerator benchmarking discussed for the benchmark tool hold here, the situation for emulation is slightly different. For a completely new accelerator architecture it might be needed to write the actual kernel from scratch. What is needed then is a framework which hands prepared input data to the

kernel. This is exactly what the benchmark app provides. So, this can already be used when the data and pairlist is laid out for GROMACS CPU SIMD use. With little effort the app can be extended to provide the data and pairlist in GROMACS GPU layout. But since several details of the optimal layout will depend on the accelerator architecture and capabilities, it is not useful and, in many cases, impossible to pre-generate all data. The setups of interest can be generated with little effort by the GROMACS developers in a co-design effort.

3 HADDOCK file I/O benchmark

3.1 Introduction

The vast network of the interactome involves hundreds of thousands of protein-protein and other biomolecular complex interactions. Malfunctions in this network are responsible for a plethora of diseases, which highlights the importance of understanding how it works on a deep level. Adding structural information using HADDOCK to such an intricate network comes with two challenges; the generation of hundreds of thousands of independent docking runs and an all-vs-all docking of the network components for further analysis. This task will generate a gargantuan number of possible structures files which need to be ranked and selected, the so-called scoring. This is done typically within the HADDOCK workflow. To demonstrate the I/O strain created by processing a large amount of rather small files, we provide here a simple, self-contained Python script that reads multiple files and calculates the HADDOCK Score. Selecting the best structures from millions of possibilities and dealing with the I/O strain can benefit from exascale computing resources both for processing and I/O handling. This benchmark is related to our BioExcel project on [high throughput modelling of interactomes](#).

3.2 Benchmark description

Here we present an I/O benchmark consisting of 1,000,000 files – docking models in PDB format (plain text file) - generated by HADDOCK. A typical docking run with HADDOCK generates several thousands to tens of thousands of files. Each of these files contains in its header various energetic components that have been calculated by HADDOCK. An example of such a header is shown in the following.

```
REMARK FILENAME="1ATN_1061.pdb0"
REMARK =====
REMARK HADDOCK run for 1ATN
REMARK initial structure: 1ATN_1.pdb
REMARK final NOE weights: unambig 50 amb: 50
REMARK =====
REMARK
total,bonds,angles,improper,dihe,vdw,elec,air,cdih,coup,rdcs,vean,dani,xpcs,rg
REMARK energies: 642.296, 0, 0, 0, 0, 4.80171, -0.512644, 638.007, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0
REMARK =====
REMARK          bonds,angles,impropers,dihe,air,cdih,coup,rdcs,vean,dani,xpcs
REMARK rms-dev.: 0,0,0,0,1.07224,0,0, 0, 0, 0, 0
REMARK =====
REMARK          air,cdih,coup,rdcs,vean,dani,xpcs
REMARK          >0.3,>5,>1,>0,>5,>0.2,>0.2
REMARK violations.: 8, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0
REMARK =====
REMARK          CVpartition#,violations,rms
REMARK AIRs cross-validation: 0, 0, 0
REMARK =====
REMARK NCS energy: 0
REMARK =====
REMARK Symmetry energy: 0
REMARK =====
REMARK Membrane restraining energy: 0
REMARK =====
REMARK Local cross-correlation: 0.0000
REMARK =====
REMARK Desolvation energy: 2.18009
REMARK Internal energy free molecules: 17670.2
REMARK Internal energy complex: 17670.2
REMARK Binding energy: 6.46916
REMARK =====
```

```
REMARK buried surface area: 1319.21
REMARK =====
REMARK water - chain_1: 0 0 0
REMARK water - chain_2: 0 0 0
REMARK =====
REMARK water - water: 0 0 0
REMARK =====
REMARK DATE:25-Dec-2018 19:07:53      created by user: enm009
```

The HADDOCK score itself is a linear combination of the extracted energetic components, weighted according to its stage (rigid-body, semi-flexible or water) which can be calculated using simple operations in Python (section 3.3 Benchmark Software):

```
HADDOCKscore-it0 = 0.01 Evdw + 1.0 Eelec + 1.0 Edesol + 0.01Eair - 0.01BSA
HADDOCKscore-it1 = 1.0 Evdw + 1.0 Eelec + 1.0 Edesol + 0.1 Eair - 0.01 BSA
HADDOCKscore-water = 1.0 Evdw + 0.2 Eelec + 1.0 Edesol + 0.1 Eair
```

In an exascale scenario, hundreds to thousands docking runs should run in parallel, which means that potentially several million files might be generated. Processing these files quickly without straining the system will require extremely efficient I/O solutions.

In order to benchmark I/O and file system solutions for exascale modelling of biomolecular interactions we propose the following benchmark consisting of the following tasks:

- (1) extract the energy terms from the header of the files
- (2) calculate the HADDOCK score and
- (3) write a sorted list which represents the final ranking.

3.3 Benchmark software

In order to parse and representatively process the required data from the header of the generated files, as a first approach we have developed a script in Python 3. This script extracts the relevant data from the input file, performs a series of mathematical operations to calculate the HADDOCK score and finally prints the score to the standard output. The returned output is a list of ranked PDB files from the best (lowest HADDOCK score) to the worse (highest HADDOCK score). The script is provided alongside the benchmark at:

https://github.com/bioexcel/bioexcel-exascale-co-design-benchmarks/blob/master/HADDOCK/calc_batch_hs.py

The function contained in the script that extracts values to calculate the HADDOCK score is shown below:

```
def extract_energies(pdb_file):
    """ Extract energies from the header of the PDB file, according to HADDOCK formatting """
    vdw_elec_air_regex = r"s(\-?\d*\.\d{1,}0\b)"
    desolv_regex = r"(\-?\d*\.\d*)$"
    bsa_regex = r"(\-?\d*\.\d*)$"
    f = open(pdb_file, 'r')
    for line in f:
        if 'REMARK energies' in line:
```

```

total,bonds,angles,improper,dihe,vdw,elec,air,cdih,coup,rdcs,vean,dani,xpcs,rg =
re.findall(
    vdw_elec_air_regex, line)
vdw = float(vdw)
elec = float(elec)
air = float(elec)
if 'REMARK Desolvation' in line:
    desolv = float(re.findall(desolv_regex, line)[0])
if 'REMARK buried surface area' in line:
    bsa = float(re.findall(bsa_regex, line)[0])
    break
f.close()
return vdw, elec, desolv, air, bsa

def calculate_haddock_score(pdb_file):
    """ Calculate the HADDOCK Score of the PDB file using its appropriate weight """
    weight_dic = dict(it0=(0.01,1.0,1.0,0.01,0.01), it1=(1.0,1.0,1.0,0.1,0.01),
itw=(1.0,0.2,1.0,0.1,0.0))
    vdw, elec, desolv, air, bsa = extract_energies(pdb_file)
    phase_regex = r"-(it.)_"
    stage = re.findall(phase_regex, pdb_file)[0]
    w = weight_dic[stage]
    haddock_score = w[0] * vdw + w[1] * elec + w[2] * desolv + w[3] * air - w[4] * bsa
    return haddock_score

```

3.4 Benchmark organization and description

The benchmark is composed of 1,000,000 structures in PDB format extracted from the results of applying HADDOCK to the cases of the [Protein-Protein Docking Benchmark v5](#) (BM5)¹, which is a well-accepted benchmark in the protein docking community. Due to the nature of the BM5 benchmark, the PDB files are different in length as they represent different molecular structures. Files are placed in a single directory and named according to the BM5 they originated from, docking procedure used, docking stage and model number, example; *1BVN_ti5-it1_167.pdb* and *1AK4_cm-it0_1601.pdb*.

To better assess the processing time of the set of files, incremental subsets of 250,000, 500,000 and 750,000 and 1,000,000 have been randomly generated. The full dataset, including scripts and reference rankings, is hosted on Zenodo, and links to download that data are available in the [distribution materials](#).

3.5 Timing examples

To exemplify the volume of I/O that is executed during HADDOCK simulations, we wrote a first prototype in Python to extract the energetic terms from the header of the different files and to calculate the HADDOCK score. The timing tests were executed using the Linux native time command on two setups:

- 1) Linux server, running Scientific Linux 6.3 - 8x2.8 GHz AMD 6320, 64 GB memory, with a 10TB RAID6 system (LSI MegaRAID SAS 9270-8i - x8 PCI Express 3.0 host interface; 12 Hitachi Ultrastar C10K900 900GB 2.5" SAS 6Gb/s 10KRPM 64MB);
- 2) Linux server running CentOS 7 - 8x2.20 GHz Intel Xeon E5-2650, 128GB memory (8x16GB DDR4-2400MHz ECC Registered DIMM - Dual Rank)

¹ T Vreven+, I.H. Moal+, A. Vangone+, B.G. Pierce, P.L. Kastritis, M. Torchala, R. Chaleil, B. Jiménez-García, P.A. Bates#, Juan Fernandez-Recio#, A.M.J.J. Bonvin# and Z. Weng#. Updates to the integrated protein-protein interaction benchmarks: Docking benchmark version 5 and affinity benchmark version 2. J. Mol. Biol. 19, 3031-3041 (2015).

and 1 SSD 960GB disk (Kingston HyperX Predator 960 GB I - PCI Express interface with NVMe protocol).

The Linux commands to execute this I/O benchmark are the following, varying according to the desired subset:

```
$ ls -U -d dataset-0[1-4]/* | head -n $i > dataset-1M.file
$ time python calc-batch-hs.py dataset-1M.file
```

Tables 3.5.1 and 3.5.2 shows the user and system time of two systems tested alongside the total elapsed duration and I/O events as measured using the `time` command. The different columns represent time consumed by user code (User), OS kernel and system calls (System), total time (Elapsed) and the number of filesystem input and output events.

Table 3.5.1: I/O benchmarking on 10TB RAID6 system

	Timings and I/O [h:m:s]				
Subset	User	System	Real	Filesystem input events	Filesystem output events
250,000	00:00:48	00:00:20	00:23:41	6,939,112	17,624
500,000	00:01:23	00:00:30	00:33:34	8,240,824	35,256
750,000	00:02:31	00:01:05	01:25:32	22,478,552	52,832
1,000,000	00:03:28	00:01:36	02:15:42	32,265,832	70,472

Table 3.5.2: I/O benchmarking results on 960GB SSD PCI disk

	Timings and I/O				
Subset	User	System	Real	Filesystem input events	Filesystem output events
250,000	00:00:22	00:00:10	00:01:02	8,011,504	28,336
500,000	00:00:34	00:00:12	00:01:18	8,003,000	56,664
750,000	00:00:46	00:00:16	00:01:33	9,963,880	85,000
1,000,000	00:00:50	00:00:15	00:01:22	8,003,016	113,328

It is clear that analyzing 1M files in an SSD PCI setup is considerably faster than on a RAID6 SAS system, with ~1 minute against ~136 minutes real time. This

duration refers to the wall clock time which also accounts for time which the processes remains blocked by I/O events. This demonstrates the current limitation of the pervasive RAID setup with SAS disks (which is anyway a rather old setup) compared to the notable speedup achieved using SSD disks.

This I/O benchmark is freely available to third-parties to be used as a co-design benchmark in order to optimize and develop new exascale file system / storage solutions for the resource-intensive tasks of modelling the whole network of biomolecular interactions.

4 CP2K biomolecular QM/MM benchmarks

4.1 Overview

Over the past decade CP2K has benefited from considerable optimisation efforts, especially with regards to improving the parallel scaling performance of its core density functional theory (DFT)-based methods [1]. General feature development and performance optimisation work have largely been driven by the needs and interests of existing user and developer communities and reflect the research problems for which CP2K is most heavily used, which have traditionally emphasised quantum chemistry problems, solid state physics, materials and surface science, etc. over biomolecular modelling and simulation.

Significant algorithmic innovations were implemented in CP2K's hybrid QM/MM functionality during the period 2004-2006 with the introduction of multigrids and the GEEP method for computing QM/MM interactions [2][3], which made it feasible to tackle a more ambitious range of problems than were previously computationally affordable. However little effort appears to have been made in recent years to investigate and explore possibilities to optimise the performance of CP2K's hybrid QM/MM functionality, especially for biomolecular systems that are of a size and complexity representative of active research problems. This is reflected in the fact that no such benchmarks appear in the CP2K source distribution, which does in contrast include sizeable benchmarks for a variety of non-biomolecular systems solved using a range of DFT methods. These latter benchmarks are highlighted as indicative of application performance by the CP2K developers [4], used in the procurement of at least one HPC system (ARCHER, the current UK national Tier-1 service), and appear in the PRACE UEABS benchmarking suite [5].

Understanding and optimising CP2K's QM/MM performance for biomolecular simulation is of primary interest to BioExcel and its users. More specifically, the project aims to develop an efficient interface to allow GROMACS to periodically call CP2K to compute QM and QM/MM electrostatic forces and use these to integrate the motion of the system as a whole. In order to facilitate standardised evaluation of CP2K's performance in these computations on existing and novel upcoming hardware architectures and to provide an optimisation target for exascale co-design, we therefore provide the following as part of this deliverable:

- (a) In the associated repository (<https://github.com/bioexcel/bioexcel-exascale-co-design-benchmarks>):
- i. Input files for CP2K that taken together constitute a **whole-application biomolecular QM/MM benchmark** with a system size and computational complexity representative of ambitious biomolecular research problems like those pursued in the BioExcel Use Cases. The provided inputs include a CP2K input file (force-opt-qmmm.inp) that can be executed directly using a regular production build of CP2K. This whole-application benchmark is included as it forms the basis for the choice and construction of the kernel benchmark that is the main focus of the deliverable.
 - ii. Reference CP2K output logs generated by running the whole-application benchmark.
- (b) In section 4.2 of this document: a description of the whole-application benchmark mentioned in (a), and an example timing profile for the benchmark generated by CP2K.
- (c) In the associated repository (<https://github.com/bioexcel/bioexcel-exascale-co-design-benchmarks>):
- i. A **QM/MM kernel benchmark** consisting of code isolated and extracted from the CP2K codebase that was found to be performance-critical running the whole-application benchmark (a)
 - ii. Other code from the CP2K codebase (e.g. Fortran type specifications, etc.) required to compile the kernel code (i.e. its dependencies)
 - iii. Files containing data structures and values of parameters generated intermediately during execution of the whole-application benchmark and required to run the kernel benchmark.
 - iv. A minimal amount of wrapper code that reads the input data files, initialises input parameters and data structures, and calls the kernel code.
 - v. Guidance on how to build and run the kernel benchmark.
 - vi. Reference output of the kernel benchmark.
 - vii. Code that was used to write intermediate data structures required by the kernel benchmark to file whilst running the whole-application benchmark – this can be included in a custom build of CP2K to generate novel inputs if desired
- (d) In section 0 of this document: a description of the kernel benchmark and the rationale for extracting it from the CP2K codebase.

4.2 CP2K whole-application biomolecular QM/MM benchmark

In this section we present the whole-application benchmark that guided the construction of the co-design kernel benchmark described in section 4.3. The benchmark was contributed by BioExcel researchers at the University of Jyväskylä and relates to the project's fluorescent protein use case. It calculates the QM/MM

forces and energies for a phytochrome dimer (CBD-PHY) in a 12x12x12 nm water box to which a Biliverdin chromophore is bound.

Previous CP2K benchmarking and profiling analysis described in the earlier deliverable (D1.1 - Specification of software engineering and QA) performed 5 full MD steps for a different QM/MM system, including solution of the QM wave function and calculation of the QM/MM forces and energies at each time step. There it was found that the performance profile was relatively flat with no subroutine an overwhelmingly clear priority candidate for optimisation and selection as a co-design benchmark. In contrast, the benchmark described here focuses solely on the QM/MM coupling interaction. This is done in part because planned development work within BioExcel-2 aims to call CP2K to compute the QM state and QM/MM interactions by calling CP2K from GROMACS, which computes the MM interactions and performs time integration of atomic motion. This means the focus of the benchmark can be narrowed since the performance of CP2K's native MM functionality can be excluded from consideration. Computation of the QM state, i.e. solution of the wave function using the Quickstep part of CP2K is already expected to benefit from wider ongoing and future CP2K performance optimisation efforts aimed at simulations other than biomolecular QM/MM. Moreover, the exclusion of the QM state computation is also justified with reference to an established recognition in the CP2K QM/MM literature [2] that generally speaking evaluating the electrostatic interaction between QM and MM parts can easily be as time consuming as solving the QM part itself using DFT methods. For all these reasons and as described in section 4.1, the benchmark presented here therefore focuses on the performance of the QM/MM coupling algorithm described in [2][3] as implemented in CP2K for a sizeable biomolecular system.

The chromophore, consisting of 68 atoms, is located within a designated QM box of dimensions 2.5x2.5x2.5 nm. Properties of the QM region are computed using the Gaussian and Plane Waves (GPW) method, the DZVP basis set (655 Gaussians), and the PBE correlation-exchange functional. The QM/MM coupling is described using the Gaussian expansion of the Electrostatic Potential (GEEP) method described in [2][3]. Bonds that cross the QM/MM boundary are treated using the Generalized Hybrid Orbital link method.

The phytochrome and waters (167,922 atoms all together) are treated using MM. The Amber03 forcefield is specified, however classical MM-MM interactions (both bonded and non-bonded) are disabled for this calculation since given the planned interface-driven usage of CP2K we are only concerned with CP2K's performance computing QM and QM/MM electrostatic interactions (forces and energies).

A nearly-SCF-converged wave function solution for the QM region is provided as a "RESTART" input, thereby allowing the benchmark to proceed almost directly to a one-time computation of the QM/MM forces and energies, which is done with periodic boundary conditions using the method described in [2][3]. After this, the run finishes without any time integration or atomic motion.

Compared to currently common simulations of photoactive systems this benchmark is fairly large – three to four times the size of usual fluorescent proteins. Running on 24 cores (two 12-core Intel E5-2697v2@2.7GHz processors) on a single compute node of ARCHER (a CRAY XC30 system) using a production build of CP2K, the benchmark takes around 200 seconds to complete and uses less than 1GB of memory per rank (memory high watermark) with a total requirement of at most 16GB at any given time during the simulation. Runtimes and maximum total memory requirements on a range of numbers of cores on the same platform, including across two compute nodes for 48 cores, are given in table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1: parallel scaling of runtimes for the whole-application QM/MM biomolecular benchmark running on ARCHER, including memory requirements

Cores	Runtime (s)	Speedup	Parallel efficiency (%)	Total memory required (GB)
1	2657	1	100	0.6
2	1392	1.9	95	1.3
6	539	4.9	82	2.7
12	322	8.3	69	7
24	203	13.0	54	16
48	145	18.3	38	26

Parallel efficiency for this particular system is poor beyond 24 cores, hence we focus on performance profiling for 24 cores to extract a kernel benchmark. An example CP2K internally-produced timing profile running on 24 cores with subroutines ranked in descending order of self-time [6] for this benchmark is given in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: timing profile as described in [6] sorted by Self Time for the whole-application QM/MM biomolecular benchmark running on 24 cores on ARCHER

```

-----
-                                     -
-                               T I M I N G                               -
-                                     -
-----
SUBROUTINE                CALLS  ASD          SELF TIME          TOTAL TIME
                          MAXIMUM  AVERAGE  MAXIMUM  AVERAGE  MAXIMUM
qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG    1  6.0    60.140    60.180    60.140    60.180
qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG     1  6.0    31.487    31.509    31.487    31.509
rdparm_amber_8                 2  6.5    17.607    17.672    20.654    20.671
qmmm_env_create                1  2.0    14.938    15.147    64.892    64.905
init_genpot                    604  9.0     7.769     7.847     7.769     7.847
qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G     1  5.0     7.702     7.813     7.702     7.813
qmmm_elec_gaussian_low_G      1  5.0     7.564     7.707     7.564     7.707
pw_restrict_s3                 3  4.0     5.624     5.692     7.648     7.759
mp_sum_dm3                     8  4.0     4.899     5.206     4.899     5.206
topology_coordinate_pack_11    2  5.0     4.324     4.326     4.324     4.326
pw_prolongate_s3              3  5.0     4.099     4.166     5.791     5.887
fft3d_ps                      40 11.9     2.522     2.826     4.673     5.086
eval_pw_TabLR                 3  3.0     0.796     4.337     4.440     4.445
CP2K                           1  1.0     0.599     0.663    203.505    203.508
fft_wrap_pw1pw2_200          24 11.3     0.482     0.500     6.067     6.415
set_potparm_index            602  8.0     0.377     0.385     8.123     8.211
get_nonbond_storage           2  7.0     0.275     0.285     8.398     8.463
xc_vxc_pw_create              2  8.5     0.029     0.038     4.742     4.742

```

qmmm_forces_with_gaussian	1	3.0	0.021	0.022	75.986	76.182
pw_transfer	51	8.5	0.020	0.023	6.296	6.658
qmmm_forces	1	2.0	0.019	0.023	76.480	76.481
force_field_pack	1	5.0	0.018	0.020	16.395	16.464
force_field_pack_splines	2	6.0	0.018	0.020	8.771	8.829
read_force_field_amber	1	5.0	0.015	0.016	9.260	9.276
qmmm_elec_with_gaussian	1	3.0	0.008	0.012	46.063	46.157
qs_ks_build_kohn_sham_matrix	2	6.5	0.001	0.001	8.099	8.100
fft_wrap_pw1pw2	40	9.9	0.001	0.001	6.183	6.547
fist_init	1	3.0	0.000	0.001	44.562	44.562
force_field_control	1	4.0	0.000	0.001	25.776	25.833
topology_coordinate_pack	2	4.0	0.000	0.001	4.587	4.590
qmmm_force_with_gaussian_low	1	4.0	0.000	0.000	67.842	67.972
qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_R	1	5.0	0.000	0.000	60.140	60.180
qmmm_el_coupling	1	2.0	0.000	0.000	46.069	46.163
qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_low	1	4.0	0.000	0.000	39.051	39.193
qmmm_elec_gaussian_low_R	1	5.0	0.000	0.000	31.487	31.509
topology_control	1	4.0	0.000	0.000	18.699	18.711
qs_forces	1	2.0	0.000	0.000	12.469	12.469
connectivity_control	2	4.0	0.000	0.000	11.628	11.639
read_connectivity_amber	1	6.0	0.000	0.000	11.409	11.415
qs_energies	1	3.0	0.000	0.000	8.129	8.130
rebuild_ks_matrix	2	5.5	0.000	0.000	8.099	8.100
scf_env_do_scf	1	4.0	0.000	0.000	6.285	6.285
qmmm_elec_with_gaussian:spline	1	4.0	0.000	0.000	5.791	5.887
qs_vxc_create	2	7.5	0.000	0.000	4.742	4.742
init_scf_loop	1	5.0	0.000	0.000	4.345	4.345
qs_ks_update_qs_env_forces	1	3.0	0.000	0.000	4.218	4.219

From table 4.2 it is clear that the subroutine `qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG` is by far the most costly single subroutine in the execution of the whole-application benchmark, taking almost 30% of overall runtime. This subroutine computes the force contributions due to the long-range electrostatic interaction between QM and MM regions. It does this by treating the QM-MM coupling using the method of multigrids and Gaussian Expansion of the QM/MM Electrostatic Potential (GEEP) described in [2] and taking into account periodic boundary conditions as described in [3]. The next most expensive subroutine, `qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG`, similarly computes the long-range electrostatic QM/MM *energies* and constitutes another 15% of runtime. This identification of the most expensive subroutines formed the basis for construction of the kernel benchmark reported in the next section.

4.3 CP2K QM/MM kernel benchmark

The CP2K QM/MM kernel benchmark runs the most expensive subroutine identified during profiling of the whole-application biomolecular QM/MM benchmark, namely `qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG`, and does so using input data and parameters that correspond to the system and simulation setup of the whole-application benchmark. This subroutine is similar in form to the first part of the subroutine that computes the corresponding forces (`qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG`), which is also the next most expensive subroutine. Any optimisations found to speed up the kernel benchmark are therefore likely to also yield improvement in the QM/MM energies subroutine and hence taken together in almost half of the overall execution time when running at a level of parallelism that was still found to be reasonably efficient (24 cores), and in a larger share of overall execution time on smaller numbers of cores.

During regular execution of CP2K running the whole-application benchmark each MPI rank - one per core – executes the kernel subroutine independently without any communication between processes taking place within the call. Moreover, execution times are almost identical between ranks. The code provided for the kernel benchmark therefore runs the kernel subroutine in serial in a way that is fully representative of a single MPI rank in the parallel execution context. Optimisations within the kernel subroutine should benefit performance of each rank and thereby directly overall runtime if changes are integrated back into the full application.

The code from `qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG` and its dependencies, i.e. other parts of the CP2K codebase required to compile it, were suitably isolated and extracted and provided in an easy-to-build format in the accompanying repository together with guidance on compilation and execution. Intermediate data structures created by CP2K during execution of the whole-application benchmark and needed to call the kernel subroutine for a single rank were written to files using a modified production build of CP2K, as this was found to be a more tractable approach than identifying, isolating and including all code needed to initialise these data structures starting from the same original inputs provided for the whole-application benchmark. The code used to write these data was also included in the repository in order to facilitate reproducibility and future adaptability, allowing data to different inputs to be generated and used to run the kernel benchmark should this be desired in future. A reference output file is also included.

The aim in this deliverable was to make available a suitable biologically relevant CP2K QM/MM simulation kernel benchmark as a starting point to enable future optimisation and co-design effort, and this has been done. With regards to possible targets for optimisation, the kernel subroutine does not currently include OpenMP yet contains two nested loops over grids. As well as other potential optimisations it may prove beneficial to introduce OpenMP parallelism.

References

- [1] <https://www.cp2k.org/docs>
- [2] *An Efficient Real Space Multigrid QM/MM Electrostatic Coupling*. Laino, T.; Mohamed, F.; Laio, A.; Parrinello, M. J. Chem. Theory Comput. 2005, 1, 1176-1184. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct050123f>
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- [4] <https://www.cp2k.org/performance>
- [5] <https://repository.prace-ri.eu/git/UEABS/ueabs>
- [6] <https://www.cp2k.org/dev:profiling>

5 Conclusions

We have presented performance co-design tools for key components of the three main BioExcel codes GROMACS, HADDOCK and CP2K. These do not cover all performance aspects of the codes, because using the whole code for benchmarking is not suitable in a co-design context. However, we have been able to identify key components whose individual performance determines a significant part of the overall performance of the codes under typical biologically relevant conditions. The code provided as part of the benchmarks is intended to be small enough that an HPC expert who is not an expert in the original application and its codebase or the scientific domain can understand the computational needs and the results of the benchmarks in relatively short time. The code size of each benchmark has been minimized such that it can be run in a simulator with little to moderate effort.

The current state, documentation and sample output is presented in the deliverable. We expect these tools to be useful for co-design and optimization of the BioExcel applications on HPC machines. Some of the tools have already proven useful for the code owners. As such, we expect these tools to be maintained and extended. Although the current set of tools covers the single most important part in terms of performance for each of the codes, it may be worth in future adding additional benchmark tools to cover the applications and/or use cases more widely.